

Regional Innovation Systems of Medical Devices in Europe

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ABSTRACT

Background: The emergence of medical devices and the underlying innovative capacity of enterprises and research institutions has hardly been studied in Europe. As innovation is not uniform across space, variation in innovative capacity of regional innovation systems (RIS) could explain clustering of medical technology hubs. Identifying the determinants of knowledge production function of RIS remains of interest as well.

Objective: We aim to identify RIS for medical devices and determinants of innovative capacity in Europe at technology level. We subsequently analyze the role of private and public funding sources in creating knowledge output across RIS.

Methods: To capture innovative capacity, we describe a knowledge production function of research ideas that is dependent on variations in regional innovation & production environment, academic research and inventory firm activities, public administration and the national environment. The body of knowledge is captured using the number of publications by Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) for medical devices from the US National Library of Medicine. We identify location of a research idea by analyzing author's affiliations at NUTS-level-3. European RIS may include multiple regions accounting for their geospatial proximity. Second, we perform regression analyses to determine the influence of public funding programs such as Framework Programme 7, Horizon 2020, European Investment Bank, European Regional Development Fund and Europe Fund for Strategic Investment. Third, based on the results of quantitative analysis, we conduct qualitative interviews with representatives of SMEs and corporations to understand role of private funding influencing knowledge output in respective RIS.

Results: First results in Germany between 2012 and 2016 suggest that knowledge production is unevenly distributed across MeSH-terms and regions. 302 of the 402 regions showed research activity with a median number of publications 2.11 per region. Average number of publications per MeSH-term was 697 across all regions; average number of publications per MeSH-term per region was 7. In maximum, 162 regions contributed to research on "Prosthesis Design". Also for "Pedicle Screws", "Bone Screws", "Bone Plates" and "Bone Nails", we identified a high activity of regions, 140 regions for each. Most actively contributing regions were Munich, Berlin, Heidelberg, Hamburg and Freiburg-im-Breisgau with 201, 198, 175, 162 and 149 types of devices researched respectively. Publication activity was highest in the regions of Munich, Berlin, Hannover, Aachen with 29,498; 19,021; 17,377; 11,231; 8,412 articles, respectively. It was lowest in the regions of Ansbach, Schwabach, Uckermark, Kyffhaeuserkreis, Saalfeld-Rudolstadt, each for 1 article. Further classification per device categories provides a varied insight. Munich, highest for total articles, and Hamburg, highest for total number of devices to perform research, have only 0-1 number of articles per 100,000 population for "casts, surgical" category.

Conclusion: Identifying European RIS of medical devices allows to understand the role of funding activities enhancing financial capacity of RIS to generate innovation output of medical devices.